

DIABETES MELLITUS DETECTION USING ENSEMBLE MACHINE LEARNING CLASSIFIER

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Abstract

Diabetes is become a widespread condition. There should be at least one diabetic in every home. This sickness is regarded as a chronic illness and is a frightening condition, which is dangerous. Due to the fact that the human body has a high amount of glucose or sugar, this occurs. Since it is crucial to maintain a sugar level throughout our lifetimes, it must be anticipated earlier in the beginning days. This paper reviews existing machine learning algorithms that include ensemble techniques. The proposed K-Nearest Neighbor classifier has got an accuracy of 87.54%.

Keywords: Decision Tree Classifier, Logistic regression, Ensemble Machine Learning, , Support Vector Machine

1. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is known to be a widespread pathetic situation which causes a serious risk to the public's health. Early diagnosis and prediction of the disease can help to prevent further complications and can take medicine accordingly. For the same, classification techniques are frequently employed. Research on machine learning (ML) has become more widespread among academics and researchers for the prediction of diabetes. Age, obesity, inactivity, genetic diabetes, way of life, poor food, hypertension, etc. can contribute to the development of diabetes. As a result, the entire bodily system may be negatively impacted and vulnerable to serious health issues that raise blood glucose levels and ultimately leads to serious problems like kidney failure, heart attack, and sometimes stroke may happen. In this paper, we attempted to conduct a comprehensive review on diabetes prediction [1, 4].

2. MAJOR TECHNIQUES

Major techniques used for the classification are [1, 8, 14, 15, 16] :

A) Decision Tree Classifier

Tree-like structure shape of the model is created in Decision tree classifier, where internal node is the decision based on a particular feature and branches indicates the outcome of decision. Leaf node is the class label. It can be used for both classification as well as regression purpose.

B) Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression, a statistical model in which dependent variable or independent variable are analyzed. It is mainly used for the binary classification for the dependent variable.

C) KNN Classifier

In both regression purpose and in classification techniques, the non-parametric technique K-Nearest Neighbour is employed. Euclidean distance as well as other distance measurements are used for calculating the distance from the new instance with other instances of the dataset and do computations on the training phase rather than creating a model. The main disadvantages of this algorithm are that it performs well during training phase but slower during prediction for a large dataset..

D) Support Vector Machine

It is used to handle the main classification and regression analysis. It gathers assortment of samples and assigns them to one or more categories in accordance with the need to which they correspond. The training algorithm then creates a model that assigns the fresh instances to a certain class.

E) Artificial Neural Network

Human brain like biological neural network structure is employed to make educated guesses about functions that depend on a vast array of unidentified inputs [23]. It is a group of connected neurons that share information with one another, and connections contain weights that can be changed to obtain the desired outcomes [10]. It mostly has three layers: The input layer comes first; neurons in this layer accept inputs and their probabilities from the outside environment for processing in the model. Neurons in the second layer, known as the hidden layer, receive data from the input layer and deliver results to the output layer. Weights are assigned to different input probabilities in this layer.

F) XGBoost

XGBoost is a distributed gradient boosting toolkit that has been enhanced for performance, flexibility, and portability. Machine learning methods are developed using gradient boosting. Many data science problems can be swiftly and correctly resolved utilising parallel tree boosting, often known as GBDT or GBM, with the aid of XGBoost. The same code can handle problems requiring a significantly greater number of samples and runs on the most well-liked distributed platforms (Hadoop, SGE, and MPI).

G) Naïve Bayes

Bayesian network is a method of supervised learning. The relationship between the variables is concealed by the graphical model. This approach has a number of advantages for data analysis when combined with statistical methods. In order to handle scenarios like missing data entries rapidly, the model first hides dependencies between all the variables. The second benefit is that this model may be used to discover casual relationships, allowing for the organization of the problematic area and the prediction of interference effects.

For producing optimal model, combination of various base models can be implemented for enhancing the performance.

Different kinds of ensemble techniques include Bagging, Boosting and Voting.

H) Bagging

Because it prevents data from being over fit, the bagging ensemble approach is utilized for both classification and regression problems. Higher dimensional data can be effectively handled by Bagging.

I) Boosting

Although it functions differently than Bagging, it is still a homogeneous weak learner model. To improve the model predictions of a learning algorithm, learners in this model learn sequentially and adaptively.

J) AdaBoost

AdaBoost creates a strong classifier with the help of several weak learners. Each weak learner have been trained iteratively and combine later to produce strong classifier. Every training instance have been given equal weights.

K) Extra tree

This ensemble learning strategy integrates the categorization results of several decision trees that have been got from a "forest" to create output. Every Decision Tree has its roots in the initial sample and then being given a random sample of k features from the feature-set and choose the best one among them to divide the data using a mathematical criterion (typically the Gini Index). Many de-correlated decision trees are produced by this arbitrary feature selection.

L) Voting

Voting classifiers are a particular kind which build a number of base models and then provide predictions by averaging results from each base estimator. Aggregating criterion may be considered while casting a vote for each estimator output.

It aggregates the expected probability or class based on hard or soft voting. The voting classifier ensures that the error is resolved by any model if a variety of base models are fed into it.

M) Stochastic Gradient Boosting

Stochastic Gradient Boosting is another type of ensemble learning approach. It adds unpredictability to the training process.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Kumari et al. [1] uses the Pima Indians Diabetes dataset, which compiles information on patients with and without diabetes, has being evaluated for testing. The soft voting classifier leverages the Logistic regression, Naive Bayes and Random Forest, to provide binary categorization. Modern techniques and basic classifiers, including SVM, AdaBoost, Bagging have been used to empirically evaluate the suggested methodology. A finding with a 79.08% accuracy rate has got for the ensemble soft voting classification.

Vijayan. V. et al. [2] proposed methods of classification namely Adaboost, Naïve Bayes, Decision Tree as well as Support Vector Machine and got maximum accuracy of 80.72% for AdaBoost method.

To increase the overall forecast accuracy, Husain et al. [3] used an NHANES 2013–14 dataset, which includes 54 feature variables and 10,172 samples for the diabetes segment. The NHANES (National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey)-suggested questions were utilised as feature variables in the form of a questionnaire.

Unhealthy lifestyle choices, poor eating habits, and work stress are the causes of diabetes, which can lead to a number of fatal medical cases [4]. If diabetes is identified early and precisely, it can be managed successfully. Machine learning methods are incredibly effective at detecting and anticipating diabetes early on. Kumar et al. [5] provides a comprehensive analysis of diabetes conclusions using both guided and unguided machine learning computations like AdaBoost and XGBoost. The diabetes research publications included in this analysis date from 2018 to 2021.

Diabetes Mellitus can be brought on by factors such as age, weight, lack of exercise, inherent diabetes, lifestyle, terrible eating habits, hypertension, etc. The current protocol at crisis centres is to gather the necessary data for diabetes discovery through a variety of testing, and appropriate therapy is given ward on discovery. Massive Data Analytics plays a significant role in clinical benefit journeys. Deep learning methods don't require any element extraction, in contrast to the conventional examination procedures that were used up until this point. We divided the knowledge base into separate preparation and testing groups in the first place.

Ramya et. al.[6] analyzed the methods such as K-Nearest Neighbor, Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machines, Decision Tree, and Conditional Decision Tree to categorize diabetes. According to the analysis, DT surpasses other classifiers, and CDT improves the significant diabetes.

By combining laboratory data with 13,309 Canadian patients' records of ages ranging from 18 to 90, Lai et al. [7] developed predictive models. Recursive learning-based machine learning has been one of the standard and improving methodologies with effective ways for categorization and reorganisation. Artificial intelligence (AI) categorization systems can be trained and tested using machine learning. Since diabetes cannot be treated and also causes significant complications to our healthcare system, it requires the greatest support from machine learning to detect diabetic disease in its early stages. System categorization is done using SVM. SVM's output has given rise to a system classification [8].

For diabetic datasets, Bashir et. al. [9] applied a variety of ensemble classification approaches like CART, C4.5 and ID3 in this work. From the UCI and Bio Stat libraries, two benchmark diabetes datasets were employed. Experimental findings and analysis reveal that the Bagging ensemble technique performs better than single and other ensemble strategies. One of the most effective data mining methods for categorization and prediction is decision trees. The suggested study focuses on enhancing diabetes datasets' decision tree-based illness diagnosis performance and accuracy. To enhance the performance of each individual tree, five ensemble classification algorithms are applied methodically in this study. On the diabetes datasets for Pima Indians and Biostat,

experiments are carried out. According to results analysis, Bagging ensemble performs better than other strategies.

Diabetes is now a common condition affecting people of all ages. The number of diabetic patients being reported is rising daily for a variety of causes, including food additives that are poisonous or chemical, obesity, working cultures, poor diet plans, unique lifestyles, eating habits, and environmental variables. Therefore, it is crucial to diagnose diabetes in order to save human lives. An effective healthcare system can be created using machine learning techniques to anticipate various types of diabetic illnesses. In this study, the Diet Recommendation System (DRS) is utilised to diagnose diabetes and prescribe an appropriate diet for diabetic patients [10].

There are countless machine learning methods available today for analyzing and predicting machine learning algorithms. The difficulty level in healthcare is eventually adding to the workload for the doctors who are handling massive amounts of data. [11]

Our dietary habits in modern lifestyles are often high in sugar and fat, which has raised the risk of diabetes. Glaucoma and other eye conditions including elevated eye pressure can be brought on by diabetes. Heart disease and a sluggish pancreatic healing are both possible risks.

Exceptional technological advancement has resulted in a significant data production in the healthcare industry. C. S. Manikandababu et. al [12] studied machine learning techniques that are employed to create a model for diabetic prediction from pima dataset. It has a total of 8 parameters, is subjected to the classification process of logistic regression.

Numerous other conditions, including heart failure, blindness, and illnesses of the urinary system, are also thought to have been caused by diabetes. Due to the time and money required each time, the patient in this condition must visit a diagnostic institution in order to acquire their reports after consultation. We now have more latitude to explore for a solution to the current issue, though, as machine learning techniques advance. We now have sophisticated tools, for instance, that evaluate data to determine if a patient has polygenic illness or not.

4. METHODOLOGY

The dataset has 768 patients each with 9 numeric variables ranging age from 21 to 81. The nine columns are Pregnancies-indicate the number of times pregnant, Glucose, BloodPressure, SkinThickness, Insulin, BMI, DiabetesPredigreeFunction, Age and Outcome. Outcome is the class variable indicating whether a patient is diabetic or not (0 or 1). We applied pre-processing techniques to replace the zero indicated missing values that are not possible for features. Outliers got from the box plot are replaced by 5th and 95th percentile values. Since the median value of insulin is zero, it is replaced by 60th quantile value. For other features, the values greater than the Upper Whisker is replaced by 95th quantile, lower than the Lower Whisker by 5th quantile. Zero value is replaced by median for the features pregnancies, skin thickness, BMI and Glucose. Feature values of DiabeticPredigreeFunction and Age by 95th quantile. We have experimented 13 classification methods such as Decision Tree Classifier, Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbor Classifier, Random Forest, Support Vector Machine, Artificial Neural Network, XBoost, Naïve

Bayes, XBagging, AdaBoost, Extra tree, Voting and Stochastic Gradient Boosting using python in the google colab. Among them, KNN classifier has got the maximum accuracy for the diabetes prediction of 87.54% accuracy. Different figures experimented have been plotted that includes feature graph (Fig1), Heat map of the dataset (Fig. 2), pair plot to show the relationships among features (Fig. 3) and Fig. 4 indicates the importance of feature at a glance. The training and testing split-up has done as 80:20 ratios for all the classification algorithms. Table1 lists various methods used and the accuracies got from the experiment.

Figure 1: Feature Graph

Figure 2: Heat Map Of Pima Data

Graphical representation of the all the features present in the dataset is plotted in the Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Pair Plot Showing Relationship Between Two Variables

Figure 4: Feature Importance

Table 1: Classification Methods Used And Their Accuracy

Sl. No	Method Name	Accuracy got
1	Decision Tree Classifier	74.03%
2	Logistic Regression	77%
3	Random Forest	76%
4	KNN Classifier	87.54%
5	Support Vector Machine	Rbf - 80.52% Poly – 79.87% Linear – 80.52%
6	Artificial Neural Network	86.45%
7	XBoost	82%.
8	Naive Bayes	74.03%
9	XBagging	77.51%
10	AdaBoost	75.19%
11	Extra tree	79.87%
12	Voting	79.87%
13	Stochastic Gradient Boosting	74.68%

CONCLUSIONS

This paper experimented 13 machine learning algorithms and got the maximum accuracy for the KNN algorithm (87.54%) and select it as the best method for the classification of pima dataset for predicting diabetes. The key feature is that different steps of pre-processing are done before classifying the data. After each step of pre-processing, the classification accuracy increases. In future, deep learning algorithms with feature selection methods can be implemented.

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